

Data

The results are presented under the following sub-headings:

Question 1: Critical thinking and problem-solving

Question 2: Transfer and critical thinking

Question 3: Critical and creative thinking

Question 4: Critical thinking

Question 5: Critical and creative thinking, and problem-solving

For each case, we first provided the relevant question, the ability focused on in the context of Table 1 and the performance level achieved by the students. Following this, we explored the analysis of the obstacles encountered by the students and how they were addressed. This included relevant extracts from the interviews and the students' written responses, offering insights into their problem-solving processes and the development of HOTS.

Question 1 (Critical thinking and problem-solving)

1. Find the points P and Q on the parabola $y = 1 - x^2$ so that the triangle ABC formed by the x -axis and the tangent lines at P and Q is an equilateral triangle.

(See Figure 2)

Figure 2

[Ability in Table 1 focused on: Identify linkages between groups of concepts, interpret these linkages in the context of a model, and work systematically through cases in an exhaustive way, with a target on Critical Thinking and Problem-Solving]

Question 1 focus and student performance level

Question 1 was designed to target and assess critical thinking abilities and problem-solving skills necessary for the development of HOTS. The objective of this question was to evaluate students' ability to identify linkages between two specific groups of concepts: derivatives of a function and trigonometry. Additionally, the question prompted students to interpret these linkages within the context of a model and systematically analyse various cases. This process involved using reasonable skills and applying available tools for mathematical exploration.

Table 2: Overview of students' response levels (n = 3)

Question number		Written Response Level		
		0	1	2
Question 1	1	0	3	0

Table 2 summarises the students' written response levels, which helps identify the level of HOTS development among the students.

For Question 1, all the students achieved a score of level 1. However, their responses were mathematically correct with varying degrees of completeness, with each student's response being partially complete. This observation suggests that there is room for further development in their critical thinking and problem-solving abilities.

Question 1 identifying and addressing obstacles.

The question required students to use the fundamental relationship where the slope of the tangent line equals the derivative of the curve at a specific point. This implies that the derivative of the curve $y = 1 - x^2$ must equal the gradient of tangent lines at points P and Q.

An analysis of the students' written responses (see Extracts 1 to 3) revealed that all three students made an attempt to respond to the question but were unable to complete it. They successfully applied the concept of relating the slope of a tangent line to the derivative of a curve at a particular point. However, only students *S1* and *S2* managed to fully exploit this relationship by equating the curve's derivative with the tangent line's gradient (as detailed in Extracts 1 and 2). Student *S1* calculated the x-coordinate for point P, while Student *S2* determined the x-coordinate for point Q. Nevertheless, they encountered difficulty proceeding further to determine the remaining coordinate points for both P and Q, respectively.

The logical implications become evident when we consider that the students' struggles to progress beyond certain points highlight the need for a deeper understanding of mathematical relationships. Developing HOTS requires not only surface-level understanding but also the ability to explore and take a broad view of concepts (Schraw et al. 2011). Their difficulties clearly arose when attempting to extend their thinking beyond the initial application of the concept. The latter was confirmed during the interview sessions.

During the interview sessions, the students' ability to identify possible applications of mathematics and their adeptness in establishing linkages between groups of concepts in the question were acknowledged and encouraged. These abilities are regarded as valuable traits that contribute to the development of problem-solving skills (see Table 1, Brookhart's abilities to develop HOTS). Interview extracts are as follows:

R: We acknowledge your ability to effectively apply the concepts involving the relationship between the slope of a tangent line and the derivative of the curve at a particular point, as well as trigonometry, to determine the x-coordinate at that specific point. However, we are curious about the factors or difficulties you encountered that might have stopped you from progressing further in fully resolving the problem.

Extract 1: S1 Written response.

Handwritten student work for Extract 1:

$$7.) y = 1 - x^2$$
$$y' = -2x$$
$$A \pm \theta \pm C = 60^\circ$$
$$\tan(60) = \sqrt{3}$$
$$-2x = \sqrt{3}$$
$$x = \frac{-\sqrt{3}}{2}$$

- Unable to solve this problem.

Extract 2: S2 Written response.

Handwritten student work for Extract 2:

$$y = 1 - x^2$$
$$\frac{dy}{dx} = -2x \text{ gradient for line AC}$$
$$\tan 60^\circ = -\sqrt{3} \text{ - slope of the line AC}$$
$$\therefore -2x = -\sqrt{3}$$
$$x = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$$

Extract 3: S3 Written response.

Handwritten student work for Extract 3:

The point p & q are equal, therefore
 $y' = 2x$ the line AB.

S1: After finding the x value, I was not sure if it was the x-coordinate of P or Q. Also, I did not have the equation for the tangent lines. I knew I had to find the y-coordinate, but I did not have the equation to substitute my x-value into. The thing is, later, after submitting my work, I asked the math SI (Supplemental Instruction) leader about the question. He explained to me that I should have substituted the x value for the equation of the curve since the tangent line AB and the curve are equal at the point P.

R: Did you then manage to solve the problem by finding both points P and Q?

S1: Yes, we used the symmetry of the equilateral triangle to find the coordinates of P.

S2: A similar question was done in class, where we used the derivative of the curve to find the gradient of the tangent line. But because the question did not provide any other information that I could use to calculate the other coordinates,

R: What more information would have helped you calculate the other coordinates?

S2: At least if we were given the coordinates of point A or B, I would have used them to find the tangent line AC and then find the y-coordinate.

R: What about the equation of the curve and the tangent line? Can we use their relationship to find the y-coordinate of P? What can we say about the line AC and the curve $y = 1 - x^2$ at the point P?

S2: They are equal at point P. I see; I should have substituted my x-coordinates for the equation of the curve and solved for y.

R: Now that we have determined the coordinates of point P, how can we find the coordinates of point Q? In your response, consider the characteristics of an equilateral triangle.

S2: We can find the coordinates of Q by using the symmetry properties of an equilateral triangle.

The aim of the interviews was to offer additional guidance on the way to development beyond initial steps and try and help them bridge the gap between understanding concepts and applying them to help solve the problem.

According to Hill, Song, and West (2009), *interactions* suggest that knowledge is constructed whilst students have interaction in tasks or assessments and receive feedback. Thus, learning is shaped through the interaction of a student with different students. In this context, interaction can

be with the lecturer, tutor, other students, or the content. Such interaction proved especially precious and beneficial while we interacted with Student S3. During the interview with Student S3, it became obvious that the student understood the unique concepts required to solve the problem. However, (s)he struggled in successfully linking and making use of them. The following extract was obtained through the interview, as the student was asked to explain his approach to solving the question.

S3: I knew that I had to use the derivative to the curve to the tangent line, but I was not ... if the derivative gave me the equation of the tangent line AB or the slope of AB. I also knew that the slope of tangent lines AB and AC but the one is positive, and the other is negative. The problem started when I derive the equation of the parabola.

R: What was the problem with the derivative.

S3: You see, (the student worked out the slope of the tangent line AB) the slope of the line AB is $\sqrt{3}$ but the derivative of the curve is equal to $-2x$, so that did not make sense and I got more confused on which is which.

Through our interaction with the students, we gained insight into the specific challenges they were facing. Subsequently, we offered guidance and provided clear explanations regarding the interconnectedness of concepts to help the students overcome those challenges. Refer to Extract 18 for the student's response following our intervention.

Extract 4: S3 written response after intervention.

$y = 1 - x^2$, then $y' = -2x$
 The slope of line AB = $-2x$
 Since $\triangle ABC$ is an equilateral triangle
 $A^\wedge = B^\wedge = C^\wedge = 60^\circ$

The slope of line AB = $-\sqrt{3}$
 $-\sqrt{3} = -2x$
 $x = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$ ~ x-coordinate of C on line AB
 The y-coordinate of C is $y = 1 - (\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2})^2$
 $= \frac{1}{4}$
 by symmetry $p(-\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}, \frac{1}{4})$

From this point onward only students S1 and S3 completed the remainder of the assessment.

5.8 Question 2 (Transfer and critical thinking)

2. Suppose that a car is stationary at a robot. As soon as the robot turns green the driver of the car accelerates, moving the car for a particular time. Upon noticing that the next robot is red the driver applies brakes causing the car to decelerate until it stops. Assume that the car starts at $t = 0$ and stops at $x = 6$.

2.1 On the same set of axes, show the graphs of three functions which represent the position of the car, velocity of the car and its acceleration, respectively.

2.2 In term of derivatives, which of your functions will represent the original function f , f' and f'' . Explain your choices.

[Ability in Table 1 focused on: Identify possible applications of mathematics in their surroundings and work systematically through cases in an exhaustive way, with a target on Transfer and Critical Thinking]

Question 2 focus and student performance level

Question 2 was designed to evaluate students' ability for knowledge transfer and their critical thinking skills, both of which are essential for fostering HOTS. This question aimed at encouraging

students to recognize real-world applications of mathematics within their immediate environment. It also encouraged students to systematically work through cases in an exhaustive way. Translate a worded or graphically represented situation to relevant mathematical formalisms.

Table 3: Overview of students' response levels (n = 2)

Question number		Written Response Level		
		0	1	2
Question 2	2.1	1	1	0
	2.2	1	0	1

Table 2 summarises the students' written response levels, which helps identify the level of HOTS development among the students.

For Question 2, the responses of Students *S1* and *S3* were as follows:

- Student *S1* chose not to answer the question and left it blank, indicating a lack of knowledge transfer and critical thinking.
- Student *S3* gave a mathematically correct response, but it did not adhere to the question's instructions.

However, for Question 2.2, Student *S3* managed to respond, demonstrating logical and coherent reasoning, and his/her explanation was clear and understandable. Hence, signifying development in his/her ability to transfer knowledge and critical thinking skills.

5.8.2 Question 2 identifying and addressing obstacles.

In answering this question, students were tasked with the challenge of translating the worded description of the car's motion into a visual representation. Specifically, they were asked to create graphical representations that portrayed the car's position, velocity, and acceleration as functions

of time. Additionally, students were expected to provide explanations concerning those functions, particularly in terms of their relationships with derivatives.

Upon analysing the written responses submitted by the students, only Student S3 managed to respond to both sub-questions. In the case of Question 2.1, the student did not respond according to the instruction given. Specifically, the question required students to represent the graphs of three functions on the same axes, but this student opted to plot each function separately. However, it is noteworthy that the student's responses in both 2.1 and 2.2 demonstrated a clear understanding of the task, indicating development in her ability for knowledge transfer and the application of critical thinking skills (as detailed in Extract 19).

Extract 5: S3 Written response.

Confirmation of the latter occurred during the interview sessions when the student was asked about whether any challenges were encountered in responding to the question and, if so, how they were overcome. The student responded as follows:

S3: *The question was tricky; when I was reading it, I thought it was a physics question, especially the equation of motion part.*

R: *What do you mean?*

S3: The question wanted us to draw the motion of the car, like in physical science. Then the next question wants us to link the graph to derivatives. It helped that I knew from physics class that the velocity is the first derivative, and the acceleration is the second derivative. So, the challenge was drawing the graphs according to the motion. I had to think about what each graph would look like.

The interview extract highlights that Student S3, despite initial confusion and challenges, successfully applied critical thinking and knowledge transfer skills. She linked their physics knowledge to the question's mathematical context, recognising that velocity corresponds to the first derivative and acceleration to the second derivative. This demonstrates her ability to think critically and transfer knowledge across different subject areas, ultimately leading to a clear understanding of the task.

While Student S3 displayed the development of HOTS, we were equally interested in the factors or challenges that might have discouraged Student S1 from responding to the question. Consequently, we conducted interviews with that student to gain insights. The interview extract follows:

R: We notice that you did not answer question 7. Are there any reasons why you did not answer the question?

S1: The question asked for two graphs representing the velocity and acceleration of the car. I was not sure how to use the information given to draw the graphs. I did not know where to start or what the graphs would look like.

R: Do you remember the graphical method used in physics, where you would convert a position-time graph into a velocity-time graph and then into an acceleration-time graph? In this case, you

were tasked with creating graphs to illustrate the car's motion over a time span from zero to six seconds.

S1: I remember that from high school, but I cannot recall how we drew them.

Student *S1*'s response according to the revised Bloom's Taxonomy (Anderson and Krathwohl, 2001) suggests that he was operating primarily at the "Remember" or "Understand" level, as students recall the concept from high school but struggle with the application (Transfer) and analysis (Critical thinking) required to answer the question. A student is aware of the concept but lacks the knowledge to engage in the higher levels of thinking.

In order to offer students opportunities to apply their knowledge and foster the development of critical thinking skills, we engaged in discussions with the students on how to construct motion graphs using the provided real life situation information. Importantly, this approach was considered following our interaction with Student *S3*.

The extracts highlight the significance of developing critical thinking abilities and knowledge transfer skills among students. It also highlights that students may operate at various levels of HOTS, emphasizing the importance of addressing those differences through targeted teaching strategies.

So far, our focus was on the concepts of limits, differentiation, and their applications. The following three assessment tasks were based on the integration content.

Question 3 (Critical and creative thinking)

3.1 If $x \sin(\pi x) = \int_0^{x^2} f(t) dt$, where f is a continuous function, find $f(4)$.

[Ability in Table 1 focused on: Identify possible applications of mathematics in their surroundings and work systematically through cases in an exhaustive way, with a target on Critical Thinking and Creative Thinking]

Question 3 focus and student performance level

Question 3 was designed to target a range of HOTS, including Problem-solving, Critical thinking and creative thinking. Similar to Question 1, solving this problem necessitated the application of various mathematical concepts, including the Fundamental Theorem of Calculus (FTC), differentiation, integration, trigonometry, and algebra. It focused not only students' ability to identify linkages between the concepts but also to demonstrate their ability to apply their knowledge effectively.

Table 4: Overview of students' response levels (n = 2)

Question number	Written response level		
	0	1	2
Question 3	0	1	1

Table 4 summarises the students' written response levels, which helps identify the level of HOTS development among the students.

Table 4 revealed that both students made an effort to address the problem. Student S1's response was not only complete but also mathematically correct, reflecting a high level of problem-solving and critical thinking skills. As a result, Student S1 achieved a level 2 score.

Conversely, Student S3's response, while mathematically correct, fell short of completeness. This highlights a commendable effort but also points to an area for further development in terms of critical thinking and creative thinking skills. Consequently, Student S3 received a level 1 score.

Question 3 identifying and addressing obstacles.

To determine the value of $f(4)$ given the equation $x \sin(\pi x) = \int_0^{x^2} f(t) dt$, we can use the Fundamental Theorem of Calculus Part 1 (FTC1) by James Steward (2023), which states that: *If f is continuous on $[a, b]$, then the function g defined by $g(x) = \int_a^x f(t) dt$, $a \leq x \leq b$, is continuous on $[a, b]$ and differentiable on (a, b) , and $g'(x) = f(x)$.* Then differentiate both sides using the chain rule.

While the problem follows a specific mathematical structure, students may need to be creative in selecting the appropriate methods and techniques to solve it. This question introduced a slightly unfamiliar mathematical scenario with the inclusion of the complex function $x \sin(\pi x)$ and the upper limit x^2 in the integral. This was evident during the interview sessions when the students were asked whether they had encountered any challenges when responding to the question and, if so, how they were overcome. The student responded as follows:

SI: I was following the steps as I was taught in class, but my challenge with this question was the function on the left and x^2 in the upper limit. Normally, we are given a simple problem, and the upper limit is just x .

R: What is it about the function on the left that was challenging?

SI: I knew I had to differentiate both sides, but now that I had never dealt with such a complex problem, I had to try to see how far I could go with what I knew. [See Exact 6 for the written response of student SI].

Extract 6: *SI* Written response.

$$\begin{aligned}
 1.1) \quad x \sin(\pi x) &= \int_0^{x^2} f(t) dt \\
 \sin(\pi x) + x \cos(\pi x) \cdot \pi &= f(x^2) \cdot 2x \\
 \sin(\pi x) + \pi x \cos(\pi x) &= f(x^2) 2x \\
 \text{Given: } f(4) & \\
 \therefore f(4) &= f(x^2) \\
 \therefore x &= 2 \\
 \text{Subst } x=2: & \\
 \sin(2\pi) + 2\pi \cos(2\pi) &= f(4) \cdot 4 \\
 2\pi &= 4 f(4) \\
 f(4) &= \frac{2\pi}{4}
 \end{aligned}$$

Student S1's method to this problem indicates the improvement of HOTS, mainly inside the domains of problem-solving, critical thinking, and the application of mathematical knowledge. His/her willingness to engage with a difficult question and try to apply his/her knowledge bodes well for his or her mathematical development.

Student S3 responded as follows:

S3: I tried to solve the problem using FTC, but I did not know how to deal with the upper limit being x^2 on the right-hand side.

R: Any challenges with the right-hand side?

S3: Not much; I just differentiated using the product rule. My biggest issue was on the left-hand side. See Exact 7 for the written response of Student S1.

Extract 7: S3 Written response.

$$\begin{aligned}
 x \sin(\pi x) &= \int_0^{x^2} f(t) dt \\
 \sin(\pi x) + x \cos(\pi x) \pi &= f(x^2) 2x
 \end{aligned}$$

At this point, the student was guided through the FTC, explaining the approach for handling upper limits when they are not simply represented as x . Subsequently, the student was tasked with

revisiting the question and, putting into practice the concepts we had just explained. Refer to Extract 8 for the student's solution. It is noteworthy that the student effectively resolved the problem, demonstrating an understanding of the discussed techniques.

Extract 8: S3 written response after intervention.

$x \sin(\pi x) = \int_0^{x^2} f(t) dt$	$x = 2$ Sub $x = 2$
$\sin(\pi x) + x \cos(\pi x) \pi = f(x^2) \cdot 2x$	$\sin(2\pi) + 2\pi \cos(2\pi) = 4 f(4)$
for $f(x) = f(x^2)$	$2\pi = 4 f(4)$
$f(x) = f(2^2)$	$f(4) = \frac{\pi}{2}$

Student S3 recognized the challenge presented by the upper limit x^2 on the right-hand side of the equation. This demonstrates a degree of critical thinking, as she identified a specific aspect of the problem that required attention. Furthermore, her success in solving the problem after receiving guidance indicates development HOTS in relation to the targeted abilities.

In summary, while both students initially faced challenges, they exhibited resilience, adaptability, and a willingness to learn. That experience is likely to have contributed to their understanding of the discussed techniques and their ability to tackle more complex mathematical problems in the future.

We continue with the concept of integration and the FTC. In the previous question, students were asked to find the integral of a given function, and in next question, they are asked to evaluate a definite integral and interpret its results.

Question 4 (Critical thinking)

4. Let $f(x) = \cos x - \sin x$, $x \in \left[0, \frac{3\pi}{4}\right]$

9.1 Sketch the graph f .

9.2 Evaluate $\int_0^{\frac{3\pi}{4}} f(x) dx$ and interpret the results in terms of area.

[Ability in Table 1 focused on: Interpret a general definition or statement in the context of a given model and critically evaluate their and others' presented solutions to a problem, with a target on Critical Thinking]

Question 4 focus and student performance level

Question 4 was designed to evaluate students' ability to transfer knowledge and critical thinking skills in solving a problem and interpreting their solution within the context of a given model.

Table 5: Overview of students' response levels (n = 2)

Question number		Written Response Level		
		0	1	2
Question 4	4.1	0	0	2
	4.2	0	2	0

Table 5 summarises the students' written response levels, which helps identify the level of HOTS development among the students.

For Question 4, the responses of Students $S1$ and $S3$ were as follows:

For Question 4.1, both Student $S1$ and $S3$ provided mathematically correct responses. reflecting a strong command for transfer of knowledge

However, for Question 4.2, both students' responses were mathematically correct, but their reasoning was incorrect. This signalled an area in which their critical thinking skills required improvement when solving a problem. Hence, they were scored at level 2 for Question 4.1 and level 1 for Question 4.2.

Question 4 identifying and addressing obstacles

The question required students to perform integration to find the definite integral of the function over a given interval. They needed to sketch the graph, analyse the given function, and understand its behaviour over the specified interval.

An analysis of the students' written responses revealed that both students managed to sketch and successfully evaluate the integral of the function over the given interval (as detailed in Extracts 9 and 10). However, Question 4.2 went beyond mere calculation and required students to interpret the result in terms of area. That required critical thinking to understand the given definite integral $\int_0^{\frac{3\pi}{4}} f(x) dx$ in the context of the integrand, the interval of integration and the area that those represented in symbolic form. To gain insight into the challenge faced by the students in interpreting the question, interviews were conducted based on their written responses. The interviews aimed to verify whether interpretation indeed posed difficulties for them.

Extract 9: *S1* written response.

Extract 10: *S3* written response.

The students were asked why they had not interpreted the negative value in terms of area. To interpret the result in terms of area, students need to critically analyse the behaviour of the function and how it relates to the integral. They must understand why the area is negative and what it signifies.

S1: I did not understand why the area was negative, because my calculation was correct, I even did it twice just to check if I did not make a mistake.

S3: Integrating the function resulted in a negative value. So, I took an absolute value of one and concluded that the value of the area is 1.

Both students' observations were correct, in the context of basic geometry and mathematics, an area cannot be negative. However, both students missed the fact that if the function has regions above and below the x-axis within the interval (like the given function), the positive and negative areas may offset each other. The integral would then represent the algebraic sum of these areas, which can result in a negative value. So, it was pointed out to the students' that if the function being integrated is predominantly below the x-axis over the given interval, then the integral will be negative. In this case, the negative integral value represents the "net area" between the function and the x-axis.

In Question 4 we looked at the under the curve. Question 5 focused on the area between two curves.

Question 5 (Critical and creative thinking, and problem-solving)

5. Draw sketches and set up a definite integral that gives the area of the region in the first quadrant bound by the x -axis, the line, $y = \sqrt{3}x$ and the circle $x^2 + y^2 = 4$.

[Ability in Table 1 focused on: Work systematically through cases in an exhaustive way, with a focus on Critical Thinking, Creative Thinking, and Problem-Solving]

Question 5 focus and student performance level

Question 5 was designed with the aim of assessing students' critical thinking, creative thinking, and problem-solving abilities. It focused on their ability to systematically work through cases in an exhaustive way and to apply available mathematical tools effectively for exploration.

Table 6: Overview of students' response levels (n = 2)

Question number	Written Response Level		
	0	1	2
Question 5	0	2	0

Table 6 summarises the students' written response levels, which helps identify the level of HOTS development among the students.

In this question, both students received a score of level 1, suggesting that while they provided partially correct responses. This implies that there were concerns related to the clarity and completeness of their reasoning, underscoring potential areas for improvement in their critical thinking, creative thinking, and problem-solving abilities.

Question 5 identifying and addressing obstacles

To be able to setup the integral, visualizing the geometric region and its boundaries are essential for setting up the mathematical model, in the context of integrals, correctly. Hence, the first step would be to sketch the graph, analyse the geometric boundaries of the required region, and understand the mathematical relationships between the curve, line, and x-axis. Doing this would help to determine the correct area, bounds and integrands.

Students needed to critically think about the setup of the integral, including the choice of bounds, intervals of integration, and functions to subtract. But most importantly, the graphs lead to the required region to be considered for application of the integration concept. Judging from the students written responses (as detailed on the Extracts 11 and 12), the students were able to correctly sketch the graph. However, they did not get the bounds, limits of integration and function subtraction correct. Hence, their setup of the relevant mathematical model, in the context of definite integrals, was incorrect.

Extract 11: S1 Written response.

Extract 12: S3 Written response.

The interview session follows:

We observe that you successfully sketched the graph and accurately determined the points of intersection. Now, please guide us through your decision-making process regarding the setup of the integral, including your choices of bounds, limits of integration, and functions to subtract.

S1: After drawing the graph, I had to find the area that I must integrate using the given information. Now, I had to check which of the two curves is the upper curve and which is the lower curve. So, the line $y = \sqrt{3}x$ is the upper curve, and the other curve is the lower curve. Hence my setup was $\int_{-1}^1 (\sqrt{3}x - \sqrt{4 - x^2}) dx$ (pointing to the working). So, my area is the bottom part of the region.

S3: I drew the graph based on the information in the question, calculated the point of intersection to find the bounds. We were told that the area is in the first quadrant so my bound were $[0,1]$. The question state that the area is bounded by the x axis, the line, $y = \sqrt{3}x$ and the curve $y^2 + x^2 = 4$. So, my region was the bottom half (pointing to the shaded area).

Based on the students' written and interview responses, Student S3 had correct bounds, whereas Student S1 had incorrect bounds. Therefore, we directed the following question specifically to Student S1.

R: Thank you. Why did you choose your limits of integration or bounds to be $[-1,1]$, while the question states that the region is in the first quadrant?

S1: When I calculated the point of intersection, I found that the graphs meet at the point $x = \pm 1$, so I used that as my limits since I am integrating with respect to x . Now that you pointed at the first quadrant, I can see my mistake. I should have calculated for only in the first quadrant not from $[-1,1]$ but from $[0,1]$.

It was noted that both students struggled with determining the correct region. This is how we guided the students to discover the correct area and establish the limit of integration during the interview session. To set up the integral for finding the area of this region, they needed to consider the area enclosed by the curve, the x-axis, and the line within the first quadrant. The correct mathematical model for the required area is given by:

$$\text{Required area} = \int_0^1 (\sqrt{3}x - 0)dx + \int_1^2 (\sqrt{4 - x^2} - 0) dx$$

The setup of definite integrals for finding areas involves critical decision-making regarding bounds, limits, and function subtraction; [upper curve minus lower curve in each of the two intervals [0, 1] and [1, 2]. Students' challenges in these contexts highlight the importance of careful consideration and precision in calculus problem-solving.

Students in the interview process demonstrated a willingness to accept feedback and make corrections to their integral setups. This indicates their ability for learning and improvement.